

EFFECTIVENESS OF NON-LINEAR READING TECHNIQUES TO THE COMPREHENSION LEVEL OF GRADE 10 LEARNERS AT BANTAD NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL, GUMACA EAST DISTRICT, DIVISION OF QUEZON PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT

This research study investigated the effectiveness of non-linear reading techniques to the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners of Bantad National High School. The results of the Reading Interest Survey were initially used and applied in determining the comprehension levels of the respondents. Specifically, this paper obtained the following objectives: (1) reading interests of Grade 10 learners, (2) comprehension level of the respondents before and after the implementation of non-linear reading techniques, (3) the significant difference between the comprehension levels of Grade 10 learners before and after the implementation of non-linear reading techniques and (4) the proposed reading program to increase the comprehension level of the learners. The research design used in this study is descriptive-quasi experimental employing quantitative method. The researchers utilized purposive sampling to the thirty-eight (38) total number of learners at Bantad National High School which served as the locale of study. The researcher designed instruments that suit their interests used as tool for measuring the comprehension level of the respondents. After gathering the data, several findings were revealed. Students' comprehension level before exposing to non-linear reading is poor. After exposing them with non-linear reading as their preferred reading technique, the comprehension level increased and classified as average. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the comprehension levels of Grade 10 learners before and after the implementation of non-linear reading techniques. Based on the conclusion and recommendation drawn, reading interest and reading

comprehension is closely related. High interests in reading may result into high comprehension level.

Keywords: *Non-linear reading techniques, Reading Interest, Reading Comprehension, Reading Interest Survey*

INTRODUCTION

Significant global developments have recently occurred, and technological advancements have steadily advanced. Alongside these changes is education, the common ground for all. The continuing modification of the educational system affects the entire curriculum, teaching strategies, and techniques. Behind the educational system are the teachers and students who serve as driving forces to attain goals necessary to achieve educational quality.

Nevertheless, with the advancement of technologies, modifications, and inventions in the education system, the world is still facing a crisis, especially in reading. Approximately 258 million children lack literacy and 774 million individuals worldwide are illiterate (UNESCO, 2018).

In the country, the Department of Education continually emphasizes literacy and numeracy among primary education learners. One reason is the undesirable results of the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) (2022), which, according to the Organization for Economic Operation and Development (OECD), showed that among 81 participating countries, the Philippines ranks sixth lowest overall. PISA is one of the international assessments enjoined by the Philippines to measure the student's level of knowledge in reading, science, and mathematics learning areas. Davila (2019) stated that "the result was quite alarming considering the Philippines is known to be essentially an English-speaking country, and it was said that language is its sole power worldwide."

Literacy got worse when the pandemic hit the country in 2020, and all schools, especially primary education, were forced to close due to the health threat. As a result, various modalities have been conducted. Therefore, gaps in the learning process occurred while several skills, including reading, were greatly affected.

For this reason, the Philippine Educational System, especially the Department of Education, urges all public schools to empower the basic learning needs of learners. The department is anchored on the newly implemented MATATAG curriculum that aims to produce a job-ready, active, and responsible citizen and encompasses different programs such as the implementation of National Learning Camp through DepEd Order No. 14 s. 2023 and the formulation of the National Reading Program. Aligned with the National Reading Program is the nationwide implementation of Catch-Up Fridays through DepEd Memorandum 001 s. 2024.

At the beginning of the implementation of Catch-Up Fridays in January 2024 at Bantad National High School (BNHS), the students found interest in reading as they chose the reading materials they preferred through Drop Everything and Read (DEAR). It continued for four weeks, but learners' interest in reading decreased as time passed. It was also discovered that lengthy stories and texts were ignored since each learner preferred easily readable, convenient texts.

A recent National Achievement Test (NAT) of Grade 10 students for the 2022-2023 school year shows that BNHS only received a 31.21% mean percentage score (MPS) in English, placing it 209th out of 227 participating schools in the Quezon Province Division. In addition, the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) results in 2022-2023 among Grade 7-10 learners implied a need to modify reading strategies, techniques, and programs. This only proves that learners are experiencing difficulties in different areas of English, especially comprehension.

Because increasing students' academic achievement and comprehension levels is challenging for many teachers and with some problems presented, the researcher came up with a study that could develop a reading technique to further determine and aid the needs of every learner. This study then aimed to assess the reading interest and comprehension levels of Grade 10 learners with a non-linear reading technique that uses a creative set of non-linear texts. To make the study more significant, the researcher assessed the interest of Grade 10 learners through Reading Interest Survey and found the preferred genres and materials that serve as instruments in measuring the comprehension level of the learners.

Reading non-linear literature with several reading routes that the reader does not have to follow from start to finish is known as non-linear reading. Junior high school students rarely engage in non-linear reading since their primary concentration is reading various literary works and lengthy narratives that align with the learning tasks. Reading with hyperlinks, graphs, diagrams, and knowledge maps are examples of this reading technique. This study then identified the students' reading interests through a survey and measured their reading comprehension before and after the implementation of non-linear reading.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of non-linear reading techniques to the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners at Bantad National High School, Gumaca East District, Division of Quezon Province.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the result of the Reading Interest Survey among Grade 10 learners in terms of:
 - 1.1. Reading Attitude
 - 1.2. Reading Materials
 - 1.3. Reading Genres; and
 - 1.4. Reading Interest Result?

2. What is the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners before the implementation of non-linear reading techniques?
3. What is the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners after the implementation of non-linear reading techniques?
4. Is there a significant difference between the comprehension levels of Grade 10 learners before and after the implementation of non-linear reading techniques?
5. What reading program can be proposed to foster reading interest and increase the comprehension level among Grade 10 learners?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed quantitative research design through a descriptive and quasi-experimental method. Quantitative research designs describe phenomena through data in numbers and percentages, frequencies, averages, mean percentages, etc. (Aprilani et al., 2023). This type of research design aims to determine the relationship between one thing (a dependent variable) and another (an independent variable) in a population (Hopkins, 2008). In this study, the non-linear reading, using non-linear text (independent variable), was used to determine the reading interest (dependent variable) and comprehension level (dependent variable) of Grade 10 learners.

Meanwhile, the descriptive method is the best tool for obtaining specific information. Descriptive research aims to describe a situation or phenomenon accurately. It can answer what, where, when, and how. This research design uses various methods to investigate the variables (McCombes, 2019). In determining learners' reading interests, this descriptive research was the most appropriate method, supported by a Reading Interest Survey comprising their preferred reading materials and genres.

Meanwhile, the quasi-experimental method aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between dependent and independent variables without random assignment (Thomas, 2020). This study acquired purposive sampling which was taken by a total number of enrollment from Grade 10. This study went through pre-test- intervention- posttest process. After identifying the reading interest among Grade 10 learners, the researcher disseminated a 15-multiple choice type of test which served as pre-test. After pre-test, the intervention followed. The intervention program lasted for 5 weeks where there was a familiarization of linear and non-linear reading, providing linear and non-linear texts, transcoding linear to non-linear reading and practice test. After the full exposure to the reading technique, posttest was immediately distributed. For this type of experiment, using non-linear texts to measure students' reading comprehension was accurate, as it measured the comprehension level before and after reading non-linear reading technique.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Bantad National High School, located in the Municipality of Gumaca, province of Quezon. Bantad National High School (BNHS) is located in a remote agricultural barangay, almost 20 kilometers from the town proper of Gumaca, Quezon, and the farthest secondary school in town. Starting from Brgy. Sisirin, BNHS can be reached approximately within 30 minutes by a vehicle called "*habal-habal*."

The school caters to students in secondary education, including junior high school and senior high school programs, with its strand, Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL). Presently, the school has 201 students: 144 junior high school (JHS) and 57 senior high school (SHS) students. The school has 14 nationally funded teachers: 8 JHS items, 3 SHS items, and 3 administrative assistants II.

As stated in School Improvement Plan (SIP) for School Year 2022-2025, Bantad National High School reiterates on improving the literacy, numeracy and reading level of learners through its banner programs. In terms of reading, the school is hardly facing numerous number of non-readers due to the fact that the learners are disengaged in reading especially when reading long narratives and texts. Based on the school's Phil-Iri Pretest for 2024-2025, there are 10 students who fell under non-readers, 59 for frustrations, 58 for instructional and 79 for independent readers. This simply reminds that there is a need to change the reading program of the school.

Research Population and Sample

The respondents of this study were the 38 Grade 10 learners in Bantad National High School during the SY 2024-2025. They were chosen because of their low performance in English subjects, especially in reading, where the use of the native language is needed to understand the topic. Since the school has a low number of enrollees, there is only one section per grade level. Because of that, the researcher used purposive sampling, specifically total enumeration sampling, where the total number of Grade 10 learners served as respondents. As Canonizado (2024) stated, total enumeration sampling is a non-probability sampling technique where the target respondents are based on different criteria.

Table 1

Respondents of the Study

Sex	Number of Respondents
Male	15
Female	23
Total	38

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Research Instrument

The instruments used in this study were the Reading Interest Survey/Inventory (RIS) and reading activity sheets with a 15 multiple-choice test. The RIS was adapted from David (2024) and modified based on the study's objectives. It is a series of questions regarding reading preferences on genres and materials. It contains four parts: (1) reading habits, (2) reading materials, reading genres and (4) reading interest scale through a four-point Likert scale with ten statements or indicators about reading interest. The statements were categorically labeled and interpreted as follows:

Rating Legend:		
4	3.25-4.00	Significantly Interested
3	2.50-3.24	Moderately Interested
2	1.75-2.49	Slightly Interested
1	1.00-1.74	Not Interested

Meanwhile, the reading activity sheets used the following scale with their corresponding description:

Numerical Range	Adjectival Description
14-15	Excellent
11-13	Good
8-10	Average
4-7	Poor
0-3	Very Poor

All instruments underwent strict validation from the experts. Moreover, the items were checked by the adviser and key teachers who were not part of the study. The results and feedback from the instruments' pilot test were taken into consideration as points for revisions and corrections.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study was successfully implemented through step-by-step planning. First, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS), Head of the Schools Division Research Committee (SDRC), accompanied by the Data Sharing Agreement (DSA) to conduct the study. Once permitted, a letter was submitted to Bantad National High School Principal and Gumaca East District (GED) Public School District Supervisor for proper checking and approval. Moreover, the request was submitted to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) of the Schools Division Office (SDO) of Quezon Province. Two weeks after the approval, the researcher conducted the study.

During the opening of classes, the researcher distributed the Reading Interest Survey to the 38 Grade 10 learners. After administering the survey, the researcher immediately interpreted the results and found the genres and materials that interest the students the most. After a week, the researcher distributed the pretest materials among

the respondents. While analyzing and interpreting the data gathered, proper intervention followed. The first week of intervention included familiarization with linear and non-linear reading techniques, while the second week was identifying different text examples in linear and non-linear reading. During the third week, the respondents were given procedures and examples to transcode texts from linear to non-linear and non-linear to linear. During the fourth and fifth weeks, the respondents performed several tasks by transcoding texts from linear to non-linear and vice versa. After the intervention, a post-test was administered.

The data obtained from the pretest and posttest were carefully analyzed and interpreted through appropriate statistical treatment. The pretest and posttest were computed using mean and percentage. The values underwent a normality test to determine whether each value was normally distributed. When the researcher discovered that values were not normally distributed, she used a non-parametric test, specifically the Mann-Whitney U test.

After finding out the results, the intervention followed. It was carefully planned, organized, and systematically arranged based on the research study's results.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After administering and retrieving the completed questionnaire, all data were categorized, organized, and statistically treated using statistical tools.

In Statement of the Problem 1, the result of the Reading Interest Survey among Grade 10 Learners were identified. The data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentage, mean, and standard deviation

In Statement of the Problem 2 and 3, the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners before and after the implementation of non-linear reading technique were collected through the use of frequency, percentage and mean score.

While in Statement number 4, the significant difference between the comprehension levels of Grade 10 learners before and after the implementation of non-linear reading techniques was tested using Mann Whitney U-Test. Mann Whitney u-Test is used as an alternative for Independent T-Test. The result of the study underwent a normality test to identify if there was a normal distribution. Since the significance and p-value were less than 0.05, the values were not normally distributed. Thus, the researcher came up with this non-parametric type of test, which also determined the significant difference between the two independent variables.

RESULTS

Part I. Results of Reading Interest Survey among Grade 10 Learners

Table 2
Reading Attitude

Indicator	N	Yes	No	Sometimes
I enjoy reading.	38	19	5	14
I understand what I read.	38	16	11	11
Reading makes me feel hard and frustrated.	38	6	14	18

Table 2 shows the reading habits of Grade 10 learners, which is used to develop texts to assess their comprehension level.

Before the learners underwent the non-linear reading techniques, the reading interest survey was administered and interpreted logically. The data presented showed that out of 38 Grade 10 learners, 19 students like to read, 5 do not like to read, and 14 gradually like to read. Additionally, when reading, 16 learners totally understand what they read, 11 students do not understand what they read, and 11 students sometimes know what they read. Furthermore, the table shows that 18 students sometimes feel complicated and frustrated when reading, 14 students do not feel the same way, and 6 students are getting stiff and frustrated. Thus, the result revealed that many students like to read; however, they do not understand what they read, leading to difficulty and frustration when reading.

According to Brandon (2021), determining words on a specific page does not necessarily fulfill the primary purpose of reading, which is reading comprehension. A child should both read the entire passage and explain what was read. In addition, Lustyantie (2020) believed that reading interest affects the comprehension of reading texts. Additionally, learners feel frustrated when they do not understand what they are reading. Thus, it is strongly affirmed that teachers must know learners' interests before exposing them to texts that suit their preferences.

Table 3
Reading Materials

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Academic Books	10	26%
Articles	2	5%
Comics	11	28%
Magazines	3	7%
Novels	16	42%
Recipe Books	4	10%
Story Books	21	55%
Textbooks	3	7%

Others

0

0%

In determining the reading materials students love, the researcher asked the respondents to answer a maximum of three reading materials they prefer. The data showed that in terms of reading materials, storybooks (55%), novels (42%), and comics (28%) are the top 3 reading materials preferred by Grade 10 learners. At the same time, other reading materials like academic books (26%), recipe books (10%), magazines and textbooks (7%), and articles (5%) are not likely to be read by the respondents.

It is stated that reading materials help keep in touch with the current world and can affect someone's life, family, and country (Khasanah & Setyowati, 2023). Furthermore, Morong et al. (2024) believe that loss of interest in reading may lead to struggles in terms of comprehension. Therefore, the choice of reading materials could develop when students' interest in reading is discovered - learners' interests before exposing them to texts that suit their preferences.

Table 4

Reading Genres

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Comedy	23	60%
Education	14	36%
Entertainment	7	18%
Fiction	6	15%
Horror	11	38%
Drama	10	26%
Poetry	6	15%
Romance	5	13%
Others	0	0%

Table 4 presents that Grade 10 learners are primarily interested in comedy (humorous), which was answered by 23 or 60% of the respondents. It was then followed by education with 14 or 36%, horror with 11 or 38%, drama with 10 or 26%, entertainment with 7 or 18%, fiction, and poetry with 6 or 15%, and romance, which got 5 or 13% of the respondents' overall answer.

The result of this survey contradicts the study of Corpuz (2022) entitled "An Assessment on the Reading Interest of Third Year Students of Maximo L. Gatlabayan Memorial National High School: A Basis in Selecting Supplementary Reading Materials in English," where the majority of third-year high school students preferred love stories (53) among other types of books. However, comedy was still their second choice, the relatively highest preferred genre of Grade 10 learners at Bantad National High School. The differences and similarities presented prove that every learner has different preferences and perspectives. The teacher must provide immediate intervention based on their needs.

Table 5
Reading Interest Result

Indicator	N	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Analysis
I started reading from the first paragraph and continued until the last one.	38	23	14	0	1	3.55	.65	Significantly Interested	The learners are more likely to read from the first paragraph until the last paragraph.
Whenever I am having trouble understanding the text, I read it repeatedly until I comprehend it	38	26	11	1	0	3.66	.53	Significantly Interested	The result infers that learners have a high interest in repeating the text whenever experiencing difficulty in understanding the text.
I continue reading even if the text consists of unfamiliar words, especially when the events in the text become interesting.	38	13	19	4	2	3.13	.81	Slightly Interested	The learners have little interest in reading if they encounter unfamiliar words.
If I encounter unfamiliar words or phrases, I look into the meaning of them in the dictionary so that I can comprehend more of the	38	21	14	2	1	3.45	.72	Significantly Interested	With a mean score of 3.45, the learners are more likely to rely on the dictionary when encountering difficult words.

meaning of the text.									
I easily understand the text when I start reading it from the beginning up to the end.	38	20	14	4	0	3.42	.68	Significantly Interested	Another significant interest was gathered when learners started reading from the beginning up to the end.
When reading, I consider any graphs, pictures, or other visuals more helpful in understanding the text I am reading.	38	31	6	1	0	3.79	.47	Significantly Interested	The learner-respondents were significantly interested in reading text accompanied by graphs, pictures, and other visuals.
While reading, I prefer if it is presented in graphs.	38	29	8	0	1	3.71	.61	Significantly Interested	The learners also prefer to read text using graphs. The indicator got a 3.71 mean score.
Understanding through pictures and representations is easier to remember and is harder to forget.	38	29	9	0	0	3.76	.61	Significantly Interested	With a mean score of 3.76, which means highly significant, the learners easily understand and remember the text when it has pictures and representations.
I pay attention to indirectly stated ideas and try to make	38	27	11	0	0	3.71	.46	Significantly Interested	The learners have a high interest in paying attention to

inferences about them.									indirectly stated ideas and trying to make predictions about that.
I understand the lesson easily, especially when it comes to graphs and pie charts.	38	32	5	1	0	3.81	.46	Significantly Interested	Among many other indicators, the learners gave the highest interest level in understanding the lesson when encountering graphs and pie charts.

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Significantly Interested, 2.50-3.24- Moderately Interested, 1.75-2.49-Slightly Interested 1.00-1.74 Not Interested

Table 5 shows learners' reading interest regarding the reading materials they prefer. The table shows that learners understand the lesson easily, especially regarding graphs and pie charts, with the highest mean of 3.81. It was followed by considering graphs and pictures more helpful in understanding the text they read. The 10 indicators got an interest level of "significantly interested," which means that learners are interested in reading text in the form of linear and non-linear.

This result is parallel to the study of Haguisan (2022) on "Non-Linear Text: An Important Instructional Scaffolding Tool: A Case Study of Grade 10 Students at Panitan National High School." Both studies infer that the use of non-linear text or non-linear reading techniques is an effective learning technique, and learners can more effectively find answers through quick scanning using pictures, flow charts, pie charts, graphs, etc.

Additionally, reading interest means different things. Reading interest could be a way for students to comprehend the text more, a simple hobby for some students with lots of books (Morong et al., 2024).

Part II. Comprehension Level of Grade 10 Learners Before the Implementation of Non-Linear Reading Techniques

Table 6

Comprehension Level of Grade 10 Learners Before the Implementation of Non-linear Reading Technique

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage	Over-all Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
14-15	0	0.00%			
11-13	4	10.53%			
8-10	13	34.21%	47.72	7.16	Poor
4-7	18	47.37%			
0-3	3	7.89%			

Legend: 14-15- Excellent, 11-13-Good,8-10-Average, 4-7-Poor, 0-3- Very Poor

Table 6 displays the comprehension performance level of Grade 10 learners before exposure to non-linear reading techniques. Based on the table presented, there were 3 students (7.89%) who fell under very poor comprehension level, 18 students (47.37%) who fell under poor comprehension level, 13 students (34.21%) who fell under average comprehension level, and 4 students (10.53%) who fell under good comprehension level. The results revealed that the reading comprehension level of the learners in the pretest is 7.16, which is categorized as “poor” ($m = 7.16$, $p = 47.72\%$).

Based on the data gathered, this further implies that a certain various strategy or techniques should be added to increase the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners. From the recommendation made by Jalotjot (2023), teachers must prioritize and assist learners, especially struggling readers, through various intervention programs. However, intervention programs must solely focus on the needs of the learners in terms of learning. She also reiterated that a firm foundation in language ability is needed to build higher language acquisition. Every learner must emphasize understanding and interpreting texts in a manner that a love for reading could foster and better academic performance could develop. Now that the low comprehension level is evident, everyone should find means to lessen and resolve the problems in terms of reading comprehension.

Part III. Comprehension Level of Grade 10 Learners After the Implementation of Non-Linear Reading Techniques

Table 7

Comprehension Level of Grade 10 After the Implementation of the Non-linear Reading Technique

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage	Over-all Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
14-15	0	0.00%			
11-13	16	42.11%			
8-10	12	31.58%	62.63%	9.39	Average
4-7	10	26.32%			

0-3	0	0.00%
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Legend: 14-15- Excellent, 11-13-Good,8-10-Average, 4-7-Poor, 0-3- Very Poor

Table 7 presents the comprehension level of 38 Grade 10 learners after exposure to non-linear reading techniques. After the implementation, 10 students (26.32%) fell under the poor comprehension level, 12 students (31.58%) fell under the average comprehension level, and 16 students (42.11%) fell under the excellent comprehension level. The results revealed that the reading comprehension level of the learners in the posttest was 9.39, which is categorized as “average” ($m = 9.39\%$, $p = 62.63\%$).

The results obtained indicate that the non-linear reading technique helped the Grade 10 learners increase their comprehension level from a mean score of 7.16 on the pre-test to 9.39 on the post-test. Therefore, the researcher can infer that the implementation of non-linear reading techniques among Grade 10 learners has a significant impact on increasing the comprehension level of the learners. Furthermore, this result shows the progress of learners reading skills from traditional to new techniques being used in this study. Since one of the goals of this study is to improve the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners, the technique used in this study is compelling due to the level of improvement on comprehension using non-linear reading techniques. Every language teacher, should find means in order to meet the needs of the learners. In fact, there are various researches about reading intervention which were proven effective.

According to Sambayon et al. (2023), every teacher must have a variety of teaching strategies to aid the learners in their academic and reading performance. A teacher should focus not only on how their reading strategies may demonstrate but also on how this strategy could enhance the comprehension status of learners.

Part IV. Significant Difference Between the Comprehension Levels of Grade 10 Learners Before and After the Implementation of Non-Linear Reading Techniques.

The following figure shows the significant difference between the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners before and after exposure to non-linear reading techniques.

Figure 4
Pretest and Posttest Result among Grade 10 Learners

Figure 4 demonstrates the pretest and post-test results among Grade 10 learners before and after exposure to the non-linear reading technique. During the pretest, the mean score of learners fell to 7.16, which was classified as "poor." After the five-week intervention process, the post-test was executed, and the learners' comprehension level dropped to 9.39 with a classification of "average." From a narrow context, the result implies a difference between the pretest and post-test results from the respondents.

The study's findings prove that the non-linear reading technique is effective. According to Hutamares (2023), intervention helps to develop recipients' reading performance and foster learners' love for reading.

Table 8
Test of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Pre_Test	.279	38	.000	.856	38	.000
Post_Test	.459	38	.000	.550	38	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Table 8 presents a normality test for data analysis to check if the data is usually distributed. The normality test refers to how the data fits into a normal distribution. When

the data was collected, the researcher used a normality test in order to determine if the data are normally distributed.

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were used in this study. These test are statistical procedure used in assessing whether a dataset is normally distributed. When the result of the p-value or significance level is 0.05 or less, this simply implies that the data obtained are not normally distributed. Using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and the Shapiro-Wilk tests, the significance value and p-value in the data gathered were 0.000. This simply means that the two independent test were not normally distributed and there is a need to use a non-parametric test which doesn't require a specific distribution. Therefore, the researcher used the Mann-Whitney U test, a non-parametric measurement for two independent variables.

Table 9

Test Statistics of Mann Whitney U Test

	Test Score
Mann-Whitney U	180.000
Wilcoxon W	921.000
Z	-6.000
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

a. Grouping Variable: Group

Table 9 demonstrates the test statistics of the Mann-Whitney U test. The Mann-Whitney U-test or Wilcoxon rank sum-test is a non-parametric test that was used as an alternative test and used to compare two independent samples. In order to determine the significant difference between the two groups, the researcher filled in two independent samples using MWU test. If the p-value is below the significance level 0.05, the null hypothesis should be rejected. From the test provided, the result shows that the Z value is -6.000, and the p-value is 0.000. Based on the result, the value is less than 0.05; therefore, the null hypothesis stating there is no significant difference between the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners before and after the implementation of non-linear reading techniques is rejected.

According to Sundjaja (2023), the Mann-Whitney U test is best when the value is not normally distributed. It compares the means of two independent groups and it is the opposite of an independent T-test. The pre-test and post test result has significant difference during the study. With the help of Mann-Whitney U-Test, the researcher can obviously determine the impact of non-linear reading techniques to the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners.

Table 10
Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of Test_Score is the same across categories of Group.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

Table 10 shows the hypothesis test summary of pre-test and post-test comprehension level results of Grade 10 learners. The significance level is .05. From the computed significance or p-value, it resulted in 0.000, which is lower than (<) 0.05. Since the p-value or significance is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there was a significant difference between the pre-test result when using traditional reading and the post-test when using non-linear reading. Rejecting the null hypothesis indicates that use of non-linear reading techniques is an effective tool in increasing the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners.

On the other hand, this result demonstrated that non-linear reading is a compelling reading technique. Its findings are similar to those of the Echaure (2023) study on “The Comparative Study on the Reading Performance on Linear and Non-Linear Text of Grade 11 Students of President Ramon Magsaysay State University, IBA Main Campus.” From his study, he proved that the use of non-linear texts was more effective than linear text. Reading should not merely focus on text alone but should also focus on the interests of the learners. He also suggested that the use of work text which provides graphic organizers, diagrams, drawings and illustrations is strongly encourage for better academic achievement and performance among learners. Moreover, the implementation of non-linear reading should be properly and carefully planned for the appreciation of the readers. The reading interest could also be a stepping stone in order to motivate the learners to comprehend more with the text and be exposed with the reading materials they prefer.

Part V. Proposed Reading Program to Foster the Reading Interest and Increase the Comprehension Level among Grade 10 Learners

Based on the result of the study which revealed high interest in reading and increase of comprehension level after the implementation of Non-linear reading techniques, the proposed intervention entitled “NLRP (Non-Linear Reading Program): Towards Reading Excellence through Project LETRA” is highly recommended.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results, these are the findings of the study.

1. The Result of Reading Interest Survey among Grade 10 Learners at Bantad National High School Gumaca East District.
 - 1.1. In terms of Reading Attitude
 - 1.1.1. Out of 38 respondents, there are 19 students who like to read, 5 students who do not like to read, and 14 students who sometimes read. When asked if they understand what they read, 16 of them answered "yes", 11 students answered "no", and 11 students who answered "sometimes". Meanwhile, there were only 6 students who feel frustrated when reading, 14 students who do not get frustrated and 18 students who sometimes feel frustrated.
 - 1.2. In terms of Reading Materials
 - 1.1.2. In determining the reading materials students love, the researcher asked the respondents to answer a maximum of three reading materials they prefer. The data showed that in terms of reading materials, storybooks (55%), novels (42%), and comics (28%) are the top 3 reading materials preferred by Grade 10 learners. At the same time, other reading materials like academic books (26%), recipe books (10%), magazines and textbooks (7%), and articles (5%) are not likely to be read by the respondents.
 - 1.3. In terms of Reading Genres
 - 1.1.3. Grade 10 learners are primarily interested in comedy (humorous), which was answered by 23 or 60% of the respondents. It was then followed by education with 14 or 36%, horror with 11 or 38%, drama with 10 or 26%, entertainment with 7 or 18%, fiction, and poetry with 6 or 15%, and romance, which got 5 or 13% of the respondents' overall answer.
 - 1.4. In terms of Reading Interest Result.
 - 1.1.4. Grade 10 learners understand the lesson easily, especially regarding graphs and pie charts, with the highest mean of 3.81. It was followed by considering graphs and pictures more helpful in understanding the text they read. The 10 indicators got an interest level of "significantly interested," which means that learners are interested in reading text in the form of linear and non-linear.
2. The comprehension level of Grade 10 learners before the implementation of non-linear reading techniques had a mean score of 7.16, which indicated "poor"

comprehension. It simply shows that traditional reading strategies are outdated and require modification with new, effective reading techniques.

3. The comprehension level of Grade 10 learners after the implementation of non-linear reading techniques had a mean score 9.39, which indicated “average” comprehension.
 4. There is a significant difference between the comprehension levels of Grade 10 learners before and after the implementation of Non-linear Reading Techniques. From 9.39 mean score, the posttest got 9.39 mean score. With the help of Mann-Whitney U-test, the data showed that the Z value is -6.000 and p-value is 000. Therefore, a null hypothesis was rejected.
 5. The implementation of Non-linear Reading techniques is essential for the students of Bantad National High School in order to foster the reading interest and comprehension levels of the learners. The proposed reading program aims not only to recognize non-linear reading but also master the way on how to read the text. It is quite important to foster the reading interest among learners then increase the comprehension level later on.
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Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that:

1. In designing Reading Activity Sheet among learners, reading interest was considered. If the reading interest is high, reading comprehension may also increase.
 2. The comprehension level of Grade 10 learners before the implementation of non-linear reading techniques is “Poor”.
 3. The comprehension level of Grade 10 learners after the implementation of non-linear reading techniques is “average”.
 4. There is a significant difference before and after the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.
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Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Since the result of reading interest survey among the learners showed that they are interested in texts with pictures and graphs, teachers and reading specialists shall consider the interest of the learners for positive engagement in reading. This includes the reading attitudes, reading materials, and reading genres.
2. Considering that the result of the comprehension level of Grade 10 learners before the implementation of non-linear techniques was classified as “poor”, each school

should create a reading program that continually focuses on increasing students' reading comprehension.

3. In consideration of the result of this study where Grade 10 learners got a better comprehension level after the implementation of non-linear reading techniques, text editors, and curriculum makers are recommended to promote non-linear reading techniques as way of developing students' interest and increasing reading comprehension.
4. Based on the findings of the study which proved that the effects of non-linear reading techniques to the reading interest and comprehension level of learners is positive, it is highly recommended that the Department of Education should craft and design materials with non-linear texts so that the interest in reading will be retained.
5. The results of the study reveals that there is improvement when non-linear reading techniques implement. Therefore, future researchers may investigate further studies related to this in order to gather a wide range of ideas regarding this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study ensured that the data gathering procedures complied with ethical standards in research. The researcher submitted a Data Sharing Agreement (DSA) to the Division of Quezon including research instruments which are suitable for Grade 10 learners.

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